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Manuscripts should be submitted thorough the dedicated email (psychology@unilorin.edu.ng) using Microsoft word, Times New Roman Font size 12 with double line spacing. The APA (7th Edition) references style should be adopted and article with reference should not exceed 6000 words.

The Editor-in-Chief

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Examining the Nexus among Occupational Hazards, Gender and Psychological Wellbeing among Selected Healthcare Workers in Ilorin Metropolis, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the nexus between occupational hazards and psychological wellbeing among some selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis. The research employed a cross-sectional design and information were gathered via questionnaires. The Occupational Risk Perception Scale (ORPS) and The Psychological Well-being Scale (PWS) were utilized in the study. Purposive and accidental sampling technique were implemented to choose a total of 192 healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis. Occupational hazards were found to significantly and negatively predict psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers ($R = -.429$; $R^2 = .453$; $F(12,284) p < .01$). The result shows no significant gender difference in psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers ($t(190) = 1.53, p > .05$). The study therefore concludes that occupational hazards exert a considerable negative influence on the psychological wellbeing of the healthcare workers. Also, there was no significant gender difference in the psychological wellbeing among the selected health workers. Thus, this study recommends psychological approaches aimed at reducing occupational hazards across the two genders would be of immense help to enhance the psychological wellbeing of healthcare professionals.

Keywords: Occupational hazards, Psychological Wellbeing, Sex, Healthcare Professionals.

Introduction

The mental health of employees across all sectors significantly affects their efficiency and overall quality of life (Ajao et al., 2025). Improving the health, safety, and overall well-being of healthcare workers helps cut expenses tied to occupational injuries which can account for as much as 2% of healthcare spending and reduces the costs arising from patient harm, estimated to reach up to 12% of total healthcare expenditures (Bienassis et al., 2021). Hazardous working conditions leading to occupational illnesses, accidents, and tardiness exert considerable economic strain on the medical services sector. In 2017, the healthcare and social services sector in Great Britain allocated around US\$ 3.38 billion to work-related diseases and injuries (HSE, 2019).

The psychological well-being of employees is crucial for hospitality enterprises, as it influences their tenure with the organization (Walbeek & Hajal, 2022). Ebeh and Onwuamaegbu (2023) defined psychological well-being as a subjective construct, subject to varied interpretations by individuals, and recognized it as a significant factor affecting reported life satisfaction. In the same view Ajao et al. (2024) affirmed that the subjective experience of positive emotions, physical health, and general prosperity are all correlated with psychological well-being. The presence of pleasure and contentment significantly influences overall mental health. Psychological well-being includes multiple areas, such as self-esteem, emotional control, fretfulness, and interacting with others (Chandola, 2016; Adegoke, 2014). Psychological well-being can be assessed via pointers such as contentment, fulfilment in life, and nonexistence of depression (Nzenweaku et al., 2020). Organizations with satisfied employees have a 30% reduction in customer attrition compared to those with dissatisfied employees (University of Michigan Ross School of Business, 2016). Occupational hazards are regarded as a significant factor influencing the psychological health of healthcare professionals worldwide.

Research indicates that Nigerian healthcare workers experience increased levels of anxiety, despondency, and burnout as a result of these working pressures. Studies have shown that frontline healthcare workers experience increased levels of stress and mental exhaustion, particularly in settings with low resources. Similarly, research has shown that among nurses in Lagos, exposure to occupational hazards, work dissatisfaction, and poor psychological outcomes are significantly correlated (Adelokun et al. (2022); Ogunsiji et al. (2020); Owie & Apanga, 2016).

Kassaneh and Tadesse (2019) characterized occupational hazard as the potential health risk to an individual resulting from a hazardous environment, representing a significant public health issue. This may refer to any factors that could precipitate an accident or illness in the workplace, such as actions, substances, procedures, or circumstances. Healthcare professionals encounter a significant range of occupational hazards (Jonah & Dahiru, 2024). The dangers encompass exposure to ionising radiation, stress, damage, infections, and chemicals (CheHuei et al., 2020). In Nigeria's healthcare sector, personnel frequently endure extended hours due to insufficient staffing and excessive job demands. This frequently indicates insufficient time for personal pursuits and familial engagement. This disparity adversely affects their mental health due to Nigeria's significant emphasis on familial structure (Ojo et al., 2014). The increasing demand for medical treatment, beyond the limited number of providers, places significant stress on physicians and nurses in their roles. If this stress is not managed effectively, it may result in fatigue, tension, and burnout, adversely affecting mental health (Kolo, 2017). The healthcare sector employs 12% of the global workforce.

Healthcare professionals operate in one of the most perilous environments (Lai et al., 2019). Healthcare professionals encounter not only conventional occupational dangers but also unique risks inherent to their positions (Ndejjo et al., 2015). Occupational health and psychological well-being constitute a sidelined public health challenge rampant among healthcare professionals in underdeveloped nations (Rai et al., 2021). Healthcare service providers encounter numerous occupational challenges, such as infections, inadequate patient management, exposure to toxic agents, radiation, extreme temperatures, excessive sound, psychosocial hazards, violent behavior and nuisance, injuries, and limited access to sufficient water, hygiene, and cleanliness (WHO, 2022). All these challenges affect their performances and ultimately their psychological wellbeing.

Statement of Problem

Extensive research exists on patient well-being and quality; yet, there is a paucity of studies about the well-being of healthcare workers who provide comprehensive patient care (Adelokun et al. (2022); Rai et al., 2021; Oyekunle et al., 2020). Healthcare professionals provide a variety of preventive and therapeutic services to customers and patients. However, when they concentrate on providing care, they jeopardise their own health and well-being. This is particularly evident in developing nations, where healthcare frequently lacks measures to

thwart the spread of various pathogens. WHO reported around 59 million healthcare professionals globally in 2020. The safety of these workers is paramount. Healthcare professionals face numerous occupational hazards, including vulnerability to pathogens from bodily fluids, injuries from needles, and infections from pathogens such as tuberculosis (Mohanty et al., 2019). They may stumble, trip, and exhibit unkind behaviour towards patients and their families. They encounter ergonomic hazards from transporting large things and psychological risks from rotating shift and strain management. Sharps injuries are the predominant injury among healthcare professionals in various nations.

Numerous low- and middle-income nations may lack sufficient data regarding occupational harm and similar medical challenges. This is due to the frequent inaccuracies in stated government data. This is especially pertinent to sub-Saharan Africa (Abdalla et al., 2017). Healthcare professionals have one of the most perilous occupations (Nsubuga & Jaakkola, 2005). This has endangered healthcare staff in developing countries, adversely affecting their health and job performance (Owie & Apanga, 2016). Simultaneously, healthcare professionals face a significant danger of blood exposure and other bodily substance (Yasin et al., 2019). Needlestick injuries and lacerations, are prevalent work incidents that expose healthcare professionals to the risk of infection from bloodborne diseases (Oyekunle et al., 2020). The spread of hepatitis B virus, human immunodeficiency virus etc. correlates with injuries and exposure frequency among healthcare professionals (Sin et al., 2016). Due to the pressures of increased workload, expanded knowledge requirements, additional governmental regulations, malpractice litigation, and the challenge of managing professional and personal life, numerous physicians and healthcare professionals have prioritized their health and well-being last (Mohanty et al., 2019). Considering the association between occupational hazards and psychological wellbeing, According to Olorunfemi and Chika (2024), stress at work can have an impact on nurses' job satisfaction and behaviour. In a similar vein, Utom and Salawu (2021) emphasised the situational, emotional, physical, and mental elements that impact healthcare service providers' wellness. Therefore, this study's goal is to further establish the relationship between the variables of interest in the selected scenario. The Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model offers a compelling theoretical explanation for the relationship between occupational hazards and psychological wellness.

According to the JD-R model, job demands that necessitate prolonged physical and mental effort include dangerous working situations (such as exposure to biological dangers, an excessive workload, and unsafe settings). Chronic stress, burnout, anxiety, and diminished psychological wellbeing result when these demands surpass available resources (Demerouti et al., 2001; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). In line with Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) Stress and Coping Theory, occupational hazards are evaluated as risks to health and safety; repetitive exposure without sufficient coping mechanisms leads to psychological stress and reduced wellbeing. These frameworks are constantly supported by empirical research, which demonstrates that high-risk exposures and hazardous work conditions are linked to depression, emotional tiredness, and poor mental health among employees, particularly in healthcare settings (Ganster & Rosen, 2013; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2010). The assumption of the two theories point to the association between occupational hazards and psychological wellbeing of healthcare professional.

Review of the literature

Occupational hazards and psychological well-being

There has been significant scholarly work conducted in Africa to enhance government-generated information. The incidence rate among 21 countries on the Africa continent (Auta et al. 2017) on 12 months showed 66% exposure to healthcare professionals' exposure to bodily fluid exposure. In 13 developing countries, including four countries in Africa, Gupta et al. (2014), there has been a lack of provision of PPE to prevent exposure to blood-borne viruses. There has also been specific concern regarding health, such as the unavailability of post-exposure prophylaxis to prevent the transmission of HIV infection, specifically conducted at Gondar, Ethiopia (Mathewos et al. 2013). In Nigeria, a detailed study has been conducted to explore the incidence rate of health-related risks faced by medical professionals. Awosan et al. (2017), conducted a study to evaluate the incidence rate of low back pain among healthcare professionals. In Nigeria, and more specifically at the Federal Government-owned teaching hospital named Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile Ife, Osun State, Nigeria, a study has been conducted to measure the knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of occupational health and safety measures. In total, 167 participants (57.6%) were found to have adequate knowledge, and 123 participants (42.4%) were found to have inadequate understanding regarding occupational health and safety.

In addition, most of the information sources used by the respondents (58%, 253 people) came from professional training. Only 6% obtained information on work ethics during pre-employment orientation. What is important to remember is that only a few number of the respondents strictly followed the safety principles described and emphasized in standard operating procedures (SOPs) and job aids. Of those who did not strictly follow SOPs, some reasons were insufficient safety kits/equipment while some were time and discomfort. Most healthcare practitioners (93.8%) strictly followed safe disposal of sharps (Aluko, 2016). In Enugu Metropolis, South-East Nigeria, 17.5% and 27.0% of health care professionals were reported to have been exposed to mucous membranes by blood and bodily fluid contact, respectively, within the last six and 12 months, respectively. The respective average number of exposure instances is 2,942,388 and 3,192,875. A total of 16.5% and 22.0%, respectively, were exposed to needle related and sharp injuries, with average injury number of 2.73 + 1.875 and 2.98 + 2.074, respectively, during the last six and twelve months (Nwoga, 2020).

In Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria, Nigeria, an investigation on waste handlers revealed that the injuries were mainly caused by slips on the wet floors (48.1%), contact and irritant dermatitis (40.5%), and stress-related accidents (34.2%). Only 45.6% of people injured on the job went to see a doctor. Seventy-five point nine percent of the participants were aware of the safety devices, and more than fifty-one-point nine percent learned it by specialized training on safety. More than half of the participants (51.1%) could utilize the safety devices, although 60% were instructed on occupational safety. What is important is that 89.9% used heavy-duty rubber gloves, but only 5.1% used protective aprons (Igboanusi et al., 2020).

Although there has been considerable work on workplace hazards and, more recently, the field of mental health, considerable gaps are yet to be filled regarding the impact of workplace hazards on the psychological wellbeing of health practitioners. Research contemporary to today focuses on workplace hazards, for example, physical, biological, and chemical hazards, and mental health, such as stress, burnout, and depression, which are more or less discrete realms of study. This work is generally conducted on physicians and nurses. Studies on various categories of healthcare professionals, such as laboratory technicians, administrative personnel, custodians, and ambulance crews, are still lacking, given their exposure and possible psychology-related discomfort. The literature is also interested in issues pertaining to gender

differences among healthcare professionals. This is crucial because understanding it will help determine institutional rules that will enable them. For example, a study conducted in Nigerian contexts reveals notable gender-based disparities in the attitudes and coping strategies of male and female employees on the perception and management of workplace stress and psychosocial hazards (Adenugba et al., 2019).

Gender and psychological well-being

Gender differences must be taken into account in this study because Biswas et al. (2021) emphasized that comparative research on sex and/or gender variations in occupational hazard exposures is essential for successful work injury and illness prevention methods. Gender differences must be taken into account in this study because Biswas et al. (2021) emphasized that comparative research on sex and/or gender variations in occupational hazard exposures is essential for successful work injury and illness prevention methods. Therefore, this present study is set to investigate how occupational hazards predicts psychological well-being among selected healthcare professionals in Ilorin metropolis.

Hence the study was guided by these following hypotheses:

1. Occupational hazards will significantly predict psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis.
2. There will be a significant gender difference in psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis.

Methods

Design, Population and Setting

This study utilized a cross-sectional design as its methodological framework. The independent variable in this study is occupational hazards while the dependent variable is psychological well-being. The study participants are healthcare professionals from selected hospitals (Olanrewaju Hospital, Al-Baki Muslim Hospital, Asa-Dam Hospital, Magaji Ngari Hospital, Delnik Hospital, Tobi Hospital, Adualere Hospital, Ayodele Hospital, and Aishat Hospital) in Ilorin city. Healthcare professionals are those dedicated to improve health outcomes. The set of people under this category are doctors, nurses, midwives, science laboratory technicians, (both medical and non-medical), personal care aides, and social workers.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Two sampling techniques were employed in this study. At first, purposive sampling technique was used to identify some hospitals in the study area. Thereafter, snowball sampling method was used to administer the questionnaire to the healthcare workers who gave their consents and also showed readiness and willingness to be part of the study.

Instruments

The instrument comprises the participant's socio-demographic data. It subsequently incorporated the sections for socio-demographic information as well as the two variables of interests.

Occupational hazard: The Occupational Risk Perception Scale (ORPS), created by Aksoy and Gürdoğan (2018), was employed to assess the occupational risk perceptions of nursing students. The questionnaire comprised 17 items, each evaluated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. The scale ranged from "1 = No understanding" to "5 = Significant risk." Examples of the items are "Risk of injury due to slips, trips, or falls at work", "Risk caused by inadequate lighting or visibility", "Risk associated with excessive workload". Elevated scores indicated that individuals possessed greater awareness of the risks and hazards present in the workplace. In this study, a reliability coefficient of 0.81 was reported.

Psychological wellbeing: The Psychological Well-being Scale (PWS), developed by Ryff in 1989, was utilized to assess a specific construct. It employs a 6-point scale (1 to 6), with elevated values indicating superior health. The scale comprises 42 items, with 22 scored directly and 20 were coded reversely. Examples of the items are "I am not afraid to voice my opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people", "I am quite good at managing the many responsibilities of my daily life", "I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time". The Psychological Well-being Scale has been extensively utilized in Nigeria and across Africa. Wissing et al. (2010) sought to validate the General Psychological Well-being Scale (GPWS) among an African population, attaining notable psychometric qualities (Cronbach's alpha .89). The researcher reported a reliability coefficient of 0.87 in the present investigation.

Procedure

The researcher trained two research assistants on the fundamental principles and ethical considerations pertinent to the study, as well as the administration of the questionnaires. Initially, introductions were often conducted, and the study's objective was elucidated to prospective volunteers. The volunteers received questionnaires, were briefed on the project, and were urged to direct the researchers to further potential participants.

Ethical Considerations

The research strictly adheres to the ethical standards established for psychological study and assessment, which are consistent with the core principles outlined in the ethics code of the International Review Board and any local regulations and as recommended by Helsinki in 1975, and as revised in 2000. These principles entail obtaining informed consent, providing respondents with necessary information, safeguarding personal data, and guaranteed confidentiality. The fetched data were used only for purposes of the study, illustrating compliance with ethical research norms by the researchers.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency and percentage for the demographic data of the participants. The t-test and simple linear regression were used to test the formulated hypothesis using IBM SPSS Statistics version 28.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

The descriptive statistics, presented in Table 1, illustrate the demographic composition of the study participants. The male respondents accounted for 102 (53%), while females constituted 90 (47%). Regarding age distribution, 62 (32%) of the healthcare workers were below the age of 30, and 120 (68%) were aged 30 and above. In terms of religion, participants indicated that 68 (36%) identified as Christians, 119 (62%) as Muslims, and 2 (02%) selected other religions. Additionally, with respect to ethnicity, 101 (54%) identified as Yorubas, 10 (5%) as Igbos, and 12 (%) as Hausas while 69 (35%) picked other religion (see Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n= 192)

	Variables	Frequency	Percent(%)
Gender	Male	102	53%
	Female	90	47%
Age	Less than 30	62	32%
	30 and above	120	68%
Religion	Christianity	68	50%
	Islam	119	49.5%
	Others	5	0.5%
Tribe	Yoruba	101	97%
	Igbo	10	2%
	Hausa	12	6%
	Others	69	1%
Profession	Doctor	31	16%
	Nurse	70	36%
	Pharmacist	20	11%
	Laboratory personnel	20	11%
	Receptionist	15	8%
	Others	36	18%

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One: Occupational hazards will significantly predict psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis

Table 2: A Summary Table of Simple Linear Regression Showing the prediction of occupational hazards on psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis

Variable	R	R ²	F	Sig.	Beta	t	p
Occupational hazards	-.429	.453	12.284	.00	-.384	4.242	.00

Dependent variable: psychological wellbeing

The results in table 2 above shows that occupational hazards was found to significantly and negatively predict psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis {R =-.429; R² =.453; F(12.284) p<.01} other prediction is attributed to other

variables. Similarly, the analysis of the independent prediction shows that occupational hazards has a significant negative prediction on psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis ($\beta=-384$, $t=4.242$, $p<.01$). The research hypothesis is therefore accepted for this study.

Hypothesis Two: There will be a significant gender difference in psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis

Table 3: T-test for independent group showing gender difference in psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis

	<i>Gender</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Psychological wellbeing	Male	102	25.15	7.85	190	1.53	.23
	Female	90	27.01	8.10			

From Table 3, shows no significant gender difference in psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis ($t(189) = 1.53$, $p>.05$). This implies there is no significant difference in male healthcare workers ($M=25.15$ $SD= 7.85$) and female healthcare workers ($M= 27.01$ $SD=8.10$). Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

The first hypothesis stated that occupational hazards will significantly predict psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis. It was tested and it was revealed that occupational hazards were found to significantly and negatively predict psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis. This outcome aligns with the outcome of Innocent et al. (2022), which affirmed that a significant percentage of healthcare professionals encountered various occupational hazards, both biological and non-biological, adversely affecting their psychological health. Okeafor and Alamina (2018) affirmed that healthcare professionals face psychosocial hazards in the job, which negatively impact their psychological health. Chinawa et al. (2020) similarly showed that psychological hostility in the workplace, which negatively impacts mental health, was prevalent among healthcare practitioners.

The second hypothesis stated that there will be a significant gender difference in psychological wellbeing among the selected healthcare workers in Ilorin metropolis. It was tested and the result revealed no statistical gender difference on psychological wellbeing of the healthcare workers. This outcome aligns with the findings of Innocent et al. (2022), who evidenced the

absence of significant gender disparities in healthcare professionals' mental health assessments concerning occupational hazards. Similarly, Ajao et al. (2024) also discovered no significant disparities in psychological well-being of men and women in their investigation. Likewise Mandal and Goswami (2022) who identified no statistically significant disparity in psychological well-being between male and female employees in their research.

However, Ilgan et al. (2015) reported statistically significant disparities in assessments of psychological well-being between males and females in their research. Yusoff and Ariffin (2020) similarly discovered that male participants had slightly superior average scores in psychological well-being compared to their female counterparts. The disparities in psychological well-being outcomes for men and women may stem from significant factors not examined in this study, along with variations across occupational sectors. The mental health of healthcare workers can be affected by various factors, including the work environment, accessibility of personal protective equipment (PPE), compensation, institutional safeguards against violence from patients and their families, job satisfaction, and incentives, among others.

Conclusion

The study therefore concludes that occupational hazards exert a considerable influence on the psychological wellbeing of the healthcare workers. Also, there exist no significant difference in males and females' psychological wellbeing among the examined health workers. This study's findings indicate that occupational hazards significantly affect the psychological well-being of healthcare workers in Nigeria. Job-related stressors such as extended hours, insufficient staffing, exposure to ill individuals, and frequent patient loss are significantly associated with elevated levels of anxiety, despair, and burnout. The absence of institutional support, including mental health resources, stringent workplace safety regulations, and safeguards against violence and harassment, exacerbates the mental health issues of medical professionals, adversely affecting their well-being. Mental health issues adversely affect individuals' psychological well-being and diminish the efficacy of healthcare services, resulting in increased absenteeism and elevated turnover rates.

Recommendation

Healthcare organisations should place a high priority on reducing occupational hazards in order to safeguard the psychological wellbeing of their employees, since physical risk exposure, heavy workloads, and emotional stress are major causes of anxiety, burnout, and depression.

Notably, the outcome implies that these detrimental effects have an equal impact on male and female healthcare professionals, suggesting that universal occupational health policies may be more pertinent than gender-specific initiatives. Therefore, policies should concentrate on developing secure, encouraging workplaces that fully handle risks and support workers' mental health across the two genders.

Limitations and suggestions for further studies

This study has generated significant theoretical and practical consequences; yet, it is essential to recognize its inherent limits. However, the study faced difficulties in sampling, as it exclusively utilized a sample from designated Local Government Areas inside the Ilorin metropolis. Consequently, the study suggested that future research efforts might gain from employing a unique sample sourced from all local government bodies in Ilorin city. This study utilized a questionnaire survey to investigate the research hypotheses. This survey exclusively provided cross-sectional data and did not collect longitudinal data to evaluate the temporal conditions of the work environment in healthcare facilities and psychological well-being over time. Therefore, subsequent research should conduct a longitudinal study to examine occupational hazards in healthcare environments and their effects on psychological well-being. Future study may be augmented by including qualitative methodologies, such as face-to-face interviews, to gain more precise insights into the enhancement of healthcare workers' psychological well-being. This proposal stems from the implementation of a quantitative research approach in the current study. A further limitation that constrains the application and accuracy of the results is considered a drawback.

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